

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

EAST HERZEGOVINA - FROM A REGION AFFECTED BY DEPOPULATION TO A RURAL TOURISM DESTINATION

East Herzegovina is a south-eastern micro-region of Bosnia and Herzegovina centred on the city of Trebinje, comprising seven smaller municipalities. Geographically and climatically, the region can be divided into two areas: Lower Herzegovina, with an altitude of less than 500m and a Mediterranean climate; and Upper Herzegovina, with an altitude of more than 500m and a mountain climate. The region's biodiversity is very rich, with numerous endemic species. East Herzegovina is **an unspoilt region boasting outstanding landscapes, a rich cultural and historical heritage, and unique gastronomy**. However, it is **the least populated region in the country**, with only 15.26 inhabitants per km² (Institute of Statistics of the Republic of Srpska, 2017). This trend has worsened **to the point where it could be called an exodus**. Highly educated people, as well as the younger reproductive population, are leaving the region. This **disrupts the age structure and leads to depopulation**.

The application of SIPs (Smart Innovative Packages) will raise the profile of East Herzegovina as a rural tourism destination on the global map. A digital platform will be developed containing an interactive map showing cultural and historical sites, households offering tourist services, tourist information and guides. It will also provide information on local events and activities as well as customisable itineraries. It will be the first local platform to process the tourist offerings of regional rural areas.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

The platform **will increase**:

1. the region's **visibility**,
2. the number of **visitors**,
3. the **income** of small-scale producers of local products.

The cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage will be digitalised by **involving** the most knowledgeable and vulnerable groups: **young people and rural women**.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

After the Covid pandemic, the world as we knew it disappeared, and all sectors of the economy experienced completely new trends, which is particularly evident in tourism. In addition to viruses brought about by climate change, global warming has also made villages more desirable places to live in than big cities.

Rural tourism is the fastest-growing branch of tourism.

The **digital solution** for Eastern Herzegovina will have **two components**: the first will allow **small-scale producers and other regional stakeholders** to enter and update their data, while the second will be oriented towards **tourists**.

The following **obstacles** may be encountered when using the platform:

- Problems **entering and updating** data due to the low level of computer literacy among small-scale producers.
- **Financial issues** regarding platform maintenance.

Future research should focus on diversifying activities on rural farms to make them as resilient as possible.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina website](#)

[Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina Facebook page](#)

[Tourist Board of Republic of Srpska website](#)

[Slow Food International Ark of Taste product from Bosnia and Herzegovina](#)

[Article: Cheese in a suck: exploring history, production area and production process of a typical Herzegovinian product](#)

[Tourist Board of Trebinje website](#)

[Tourist Board of Bileća Facebook page](#)

[Tourist Board of Gacko Facebook page](#)

[Tourist Board of Nevesinje website](#)

[Tourist Board of Kalinovik website](#)

[The most beautiful village Bratač Facebook page](#)

[Book: Nutritional and Health Aspects of Food in the Balkans](#)

